

A STUDY OF TURNAROUND TIME IN E- RECRUITMENT PROCESS AT CAFE COFFEE DAY (CCD)

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ABSTRACT

Turnaround time in recruitment refers to the total time taken in the entire process. This time starts when a requisition is made to for a vacant position to the time when the candidate actually joins the organization. The use of internet to select candidates from a database makes this process to be known as e- recruitment. The study was carried out at Cafe Coffee Day (CCD). The study was to determine the time taken in the e-recruitment process. The purpose of this study was to benchmark the recruitment process time for the division. The data gathered during this process was from secondary sources. Data had to be collected from the requisitions made and the downloaded resumes of the candidates from the online job portal. Data was collected from the time the company started using online portal to source resumes i.e. from January 20 till June 21. The data collected was analyzed by SPSS. The research type was analytical because existing data was used to make a critical evaluation of the e-recruitment process.

KEYWORDS: *Turnaround Time, Recruitment, SPSS, Survey, Café Coffee Day*

INTRODUCTION

Recruitment is the process of placing the right person at the right place at the right time with the least possible cost. Recruitment is understood as the process of searching for and obtaining applicants for jobs, from among them the right people can be selected. Though theoretically recruitment process is said to end with the receipt of applications, in practice the activity extends to the screening of applications so as to eliminate those who are not qualified for the job. Different purpose and importance of recruitment can be summarized as to determine the present and future requirements in conjunction with personnel planning and job analysis activities; Increase the pool of job candidates at minimum cost; Reduce the probability that job applicants once selected would leave shortly; Meet legal and social obligations; Identify and prepare potential job applicants; Evaluate effectiveness of various recruitment techniques and sources for job applicants. There are basically two different sources of recruitment, Internal and External sources. Internal sources include present permanent employees, present temporary/casual employees, retrenched or retired employees, dependents of deceased, disabled, retired and present employees. External sources include colleges, internet, references, consultants, trade Unions, advertisements, and walk- ins.

Objectives

- To determine the time taken in the e- recruitment process for each level of position.
- To study the average number of candidates screened for various positions.
- To inspect relation between the mode of recruitment and time taken.

The positions studied were classified into level 1, level 2 and level 3 positions. The different modes of recruitment were e- recruitment, consultants and other sources which included reference, transfers, promotions etc.

RECENT TRENDS IN RECRUITMENT

Outsourcing

In India, the HR processes are being outsourced from more than a decade now. A company may draw required personnel from outsourcing firms. The outsourcing firms help the organization by the initial screening of the candidates according to the needs of the organization and creating a suitable pool of talent for the final selection by the organization. Outsourcing firms develop their human resource pool by employing people for them and make available personnel to various companies as per their needs. In turn, the outsourcing firms or the intermediaries charge the organizations for their services.

Poaching/Raiding

“Buying talent” (rather than developing it) is the latest mantra being followed by the organizations today. Poaching means employing a competent and experienced person already working with another reputed company in the same or different industry; the organization might be a competitor in the industry. A company can attract talent from another firm by offering attractive pay packages and other terms and conditions, better than the current employer of the candidate. But it is seen as an unethical practice and not openly talked about. Indian software and the retail sector are the sectors facing the most severe brunt of poaching today. It has become a challenge for human resource managers to face and tackle poaching, as it weakens the competitive strength of the firm.

E-Recruitment

Many big organizations use Internet as a source of recruitment. E- Recruitment is the use of technology to assist the recruitment process. They advertise job vacancies through worldwide web. The job seekers send their applications or curriculum vitae i.e., CV through e mail using the Internet. Alternatively, job seekers place their CVs in worldwide web, which can be drawn by prospective employees depending upon their requirements. Advantages of E-Recruitment are low cost, no intermediaries, reduction in time for recruitment, recruitment of right type of people and efficiency of recruitment process.

DESIGN OF STUDY

Data Source

The entire recruitment process takes place from the headquarter of Café Coffee Day (CCD) from January 2020 to June 2021. CCD started downloading resumes of suitable candidates from online job portal for filling up of various positions for various locations in the organization. Downloaded resumes of these candidates and requisitions made for vacancies were

obtained (from January 2021 – June 2021). Simultaneously company was recruiting through other modes of recruitment. The company adopts a centralized recruitment process from Bangalore.

Objectives

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- To study the average number of candidates screened for various positions.
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Purpose of Study: To standardize the e- recruitment process.

Research Type: Analytical

Scope of Study is limited to the Cafe Coffee Day (CCD) organization.

Data Collection: Secondary data (from January 2021- June 2021)

Analytical Tool Used: SPSS, EXCEL

Limitation of Study: Findings applicable only to Cafe Coffee Day (CCD) and cannot be generalized.

RESULTS

Number of Suspects per Position

Table 1

Position	Frequency	No of Posts	Average
Operations executive	137	19	7.21
Sr. operations executive	84	14	7
Operations manager	43	6	7.1
City head	49	7	7
Territory manager	22	2	11
Operations GM	14	3	4.6
Sr. Business development ex	41	4	10.2
Business development ex	137	14	9.7
Business development manager	19	2	9.1
F&B executive	40	5	8
Sr. F&B executive	18	3	6
F&B manager	10	0	0
GM F&B	7	1	7
Marketing executive	46	5	9.2
Sr. Marketing executive	6	1	6
Marketing manager	14	2	7
Finance executive	72	9	9
Data entry	30	4	7.5
MIS executive	67	8	6.3
MIS manager	5	1	5
Maintenance executive	39	5	7.8
Maintenance manager	14	2	7
Procurements executive	25	3	8.3
Procurements manager	9	1	9
HR executive	22	3	7.3
HR manager	8	1	8

Table 1: Contd.,

Asst. manager procurements	11	1	11
Asst. manager finance	6	1	6
Graduate management trainee	44	6	7.3
Regional manager operations	11	1	11
Internal audit executive	35	6	5.8
Projects executive	79	11	7.1
SCM executive	55	6	9.1
SCM manager	24	3	8
Asst manager marketing	6	1	6
Sr. projects executive	29	3	9.6
Franchise executive	27	4	6.7
Franchise manager	17	2	8.5
Asst. manager F&B	24	3	8
Asst. manager Business development	5	1	5
Asst. manager SCM	9	1	9
Total	1360	178	

Table 2

Telephone	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Available	914	67.2	67.2	67.2
Not interested	92	6.8	6.8	74.0
Wrong no.	54	4.0	4.0	77.9
Not available	50	3.7	3.7	81.6
Not responding	211	15.5	15.5	97.1
Other	39	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	1360	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: It is interesting to note that when the calls are made to the suspects about 67% of them are available to talk and are interested in the position, while 15.5% do not respond to the call made.

Gender

Table 3

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	1312	96.5	96.5	96.5
Female	48	3.5	3.5	100.0
Total	1360	100.0	100.0	

Table 4

Experience	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-2	627	46.1	46.1	46.1
2-4	474	34.9	34.9	81.0
4-6	174	12.8	12.8	93.8
6-8	70	5.1	5.1	98.9
8-10	12	.9	.9	99.8
Above 10	3	.2	.2	100.0
Total	1360	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Most of the suspects for recruitment are males (96.5%)

EXPERIENCE

Interpretation: It is observed that about 46% of the suspects have an experience of 0-2 years.

Mode of Recruitment

Figure 1

Correlation between Total Days and Mode of Recruitment

Table 5

		Total Days	Mode of Recruitment
Total days	Pearson Correlation	1	-.007
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.795
	N	1360	1360
Mode of recruitment	Pearson Correlation	-.007	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.795	
	N	1360	1360

Interpretation: It is observed that there is no correlation between Mode of recruitment and the total days taken for recruitment.

Comparison between Modes of Recruitment for Level 1

Table 6

Position	E-Recruitment		Consultants		Other	
	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No
OPERATIONS EXECUTIVE	34	9	25	3	36	7
SR. OPERATIONS EXECUTIVE	35	6	38	2	34	6
SR. BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT EX	35	2	0	0	43	2
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT EX	34	8	22	2	35	6
F&B EXECUTIVE	38	4	42	1	0	0
SR. F&B EXECUTIVE	31	1	0	0	37	2
MARKETING EX	40	2	0	0	35	3
SR. MARKETING EX	31	1	0	0	0	0
FINANCE EX	38	6	35	1	28	2
DATA ENTRY EX	27	2	43	1	8	1
MIS EXECUTIVE	30	3	32	2	41	3
MAINTENANCE EX	0	0	27	1	36	4
PROCUREMENTS EX	51	1	30	1	41	1

Table 6: Contd.,

HR EXECUTIVE	38	1	44	1	35	1
GRADUATE MANAGEMENT TRAINEE	33	3	0	0	37	3
INTERNAL AUDIT EX	34	3	22	1	42	2
PROJECTS EX	37	7	36	2	42	2
SCM EXECUTIVE	32	5	0	0	40	1
SR. PROJECTS EX	41	1	44	1	38	1
FRANCHISE EXECUTIVE	38	3	0	0	35	1
SR. SCM EXECUTIVE	0	0	0	0	37	1

Interpretation: It is interesting to know that 50% of the vacancies for level 1 were filled through e- recruitment. (68/136). About 14% Vacancies for level 1 were filled by consultants (19/136). More than 65% of the posts for finance executive & projects executive were filled by e- recruitment. 80% of the vacancies for maintenance Executive were filled through other means.

Comparison between Modes of Recruitment for Level 2

Table 7

Position	E-Recruitment		Consultants		Other	
	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No
OPERATIONS MANAGER	39	3	38	1	36	2
TERRITORY MANAGER	33	1	0	0	42	1
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT MANAGER	34	1	0	0	28	1
F&B MANAGER	0	0	0	0	0	0
MARKETING MANAGER	33	1	0	0	31	1
FINANCE MANAGER	0	0	0	0	31	1
MIS MANAGER	34	1	0	0	0	0
MAINTENANCE MANAGER	48	1	0	0	36	1
PROCUREMENTS MANAGER	53	1	0	0	0	0
HR MANAGER	25	1	0	0	0	0
ASST. MANAGER PROCUREMENTS	0	0	0	0	31	1
ASST. MANAGER FINANCE	33	1	0	0	0	0
SCM MANAGER	48	1	0	0	34	2
ASST MANAGER MARKETING	33	1	0	0	0	0
RANCHISE MANAGER	35	1	0	0	45	1
ASST MANAGER F&B	0	0	18	1	32	2
ASST MANAGER BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	44	1	0	0	0	0

Interpretation: Total no. Of vacancies for level 2 were 30 of which 50% were filled by e-recruitment and 49% by others and 1% by Consultants. Asst. Manager marketing & Asst manager Business Development were exclusively filled by e- recruitment. The post of Asst. Manager F&B was filled in 18 days, whereas the same post took 32 days to fill by other means.

Comparison between Modes of Recruitment for Level 3

Table 8

Position	E-Recruitment		Consultants		Other	
	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No
CITY HEAD	39	3	0	0	35	4
OPERATIONS GM	32	1	49	1	33	1
F&B GM	37	1	0	0	0	0
REGIONAL MANAGER OPERATIONS	38	1	0	0	0	0

Interpretation: It is interesting to note that 50% of the posts for Level 3 were filled by e- recruitment. The lone post filled by Consultants was of operations GM that too with 49 days.

TURNAROUND TIME

Mode of Recruitment * Level

Table 9

Level	E- Recruitment		Consultants		Others	
	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No.	Avg. Days	No.
LEVEL 1	35.11	68	32.52	19	36.06	49
LEVEL 2	38	15	28	2	34.46	13
LEVEL 3	37.3	6	49	1	34.6	5

Interpretation: It is interesting to note that for Level 1 & Level 2 positions consultants take fewer days compared to e- recruitment, but for level 3 positions other means take less time. E- recruitment lags behind in all 3 levels of recruitment.

TURNAROUND TIME

Mode of Recruitment Vs Level

Figure 2

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the three modes of recruitment at 3 different levels of Positions.

ANOVA for Level 1

Table 10

SOURCE	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Mode of Recruitment	1806.000	2	903.000	4.291	.018
Error	12627.714	60	210.462		
Total	14433.714	62			

Interpretation: ANOVA table indicates that the 'f' value is significant. Therefore h_0 is accepted. This shows that there is no significant difference in 3 modes of recruitment at level 1.

ANOVA for Level 2

Table 11

SOURCE	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Mode of recruitment	5794.353	2	2897.176	11.664	.000
Error	11922.353	48	248.382		
Total	17716.706	50			

Interpretation: ANOVA table indicates that the 'f' value is significant. Therefore h_0 is accepted. This shows that there is no significant difference in 3 modes of recruitment at level 2.

ANOVA for Level 3

Table 12

SOURCE	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Mode of recruitment	1321.167	2	660.583	1.990	.192
Error	2987.750	9	331.972		
Total	4308.917	11			

Interpretation: ANOVA table indicates that the 'f' value is not significant. Therefore h_0 is rejected. This shows that there is significant difference in 3 modes of recruitment at level 3.

FINDINGS

- It is interesting to note that for Level 3 & Level 2 positions consultants take fewer days compared to e-recruitment, but for Level 1 positions other means take less time. E- recruitment lags behind in all 3 levels of recruitment.
- The study reveals that exactly 50% of the company vacancies are filled due to e- recruitment.
- It is observed that there is no correlation between Mode of recruitment and the total days taken for recruitment.
- Study shows that there is significant difference in 3 modes of recruitment at Level 3 positions.
- It is interesting to note that when the calls are made to the suspects about 67% of them are available to talk and are interested in the position, while 15.5% do not respond to the call made.
- It is observed that most of the positions recruited through e- recruitment are for the position of operations executive.

SUGGESTIONS

- Create a website where candidates can apply directly. This site should also show the current job openings. This will help to increase the number of prospective candidates for selection as currently the average number of candidates available is only 7 from e- recruitment.
- Online psychometric profiling can be done to filter out th candidates. This will fasten the recruitment process. Also this will lead to exact placement of the candidate in th right kind of job.

CONCLUSIONS

The time taken to recruit candidates by e- recruitment was found out to be approximately 35 days. As other methods also take almost the same time it is advisable to continue with e- recruitment as it appears to be a less expensive method of recruitment. Further work can be carried out to find out the cost involved in the e- recruitment process and make a comparative study of the modes of recruitment.

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